

Teaching competencies and entrepreneurial performance among the Hashemite University faculty members

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 7, 2024

Revised Jun 16, 2025

Accepted Jun 21, 2025

Keywords:

Entrepreneurial performance

Faculty members

Quality assurance

Teaching competencies

The Hashemite University

ABSTRACT

The study examines the application of teaching competencies among faculty members at Hashemite University and investigates their relationship with perceived entrepreneurial performance within a quality assurance framework. Using a descriptive-relational survey design, a sample of 340 faculty members was selected through stratified sampling during the first semester of the 2022/2023 academic year. Data were collected via a validated questionnaire measuring teaching competencies across five domains—personal, academic, administrative, cultural, and professional—and entrepreneurial performance. The findings indicated that both teaching competencies and entrepreneurial performance were at a moderate level. A positive and statistically significant relationship was identified across all competency dimensions and entrepreneurial performance, suggesting that enhanced competencies can positively impact entrepreneurial outcomes. Based on these results, the study recommends integrating teaching competency evaluations into university quality assurance policies and suggests combining intrinsic and extrinsic incentives to foster faculty productivity. These recommendations offer valuable insights for enhancing academic standards and fostering entrepreneurial skills among faculty in higher education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions play a pivotal role in developing human capital and fostering intellectual excellence. Their core mission includes community engagement, knowledge advancement, and professional training, ensuring that individuals acquire both theoretical and practical skills [1]. Beyond academics, universities serve as hubs of innovation, nurturing creativity and research that contribute to societal progress. They shape professionals who drive economic and technological advancements while promoting cultural and intellectual exchange. In today's rapidly evolving world, university teaching requires educators to cultivate critical thinking, analytical skills, and independent problem-solving among students. To achieve this, faculty members must continuously refine their competencies, integrating new pedagogical techniques and adapting to emerging educational trends [2]. This ongoing development ensures that higher education remains relevant and responsive to societal and industry needs.

A professor's role extends beyond conventional teaching, encompassing research, mentorship, service, and administrative responsibilities [3]. Balancing these diverse duties requires expertise, adaptability, and a commitment to continuous learning. Academic research is fundamental, as it contributes to knowledge creation and enhances faculty credibility in their respective fields. Furthermore, professors who actively engage in research are better equipped to bring real-world insights into the classroom, enriching the learning experience. Faculty competencies directly influence their entrepreneurial performance, necessitating institutional support for professional growth [4]. Effective educators employ innovative teaching strategies, create engaging curricula, and incorporate experiential learning to maximize student success. Studies on teaching competencies emphasize a combination of knowledge, skills, and behaviors essential for achieving educational goals [5]–[7]. These competencies are categorized into teaching methodologies, human interaction, planning, implementation, evaluation, and technological skills, all of which are integral to effective instruction [8], [9].

Teaching competencies significantly enhance faculty effectiveness by fostering student engagement, adapting to evolving educational needs, and integrating innovative instructional approaches [10], [11]. Professors must master lesson planning, communication techniques, and assessment strategies to create meaningful learning experiences. A well-structured lesson not only ensures clarity and organization but also aligns with student learning objectives, promoting active participation. In the modern classroom, technological proficiency is indispensable, as digital tools facilitate interactive teaching and collaborative learning [12], [13]. With advancements in e-learning platforms, artificial intelligence, and blended learning models, educators must develop digital literacy to enhance accessibility and inclusivity. This shift in education ensures that students receive diverse, engaging, and flexible learning opportunities, making academic institutions more dynamic and adaptable.

The growing emphasis on academic entrepreneurship has transformed higher education institutions into hubs of innovation and knowledge commercialization [14]. Entrepreneurial universities encourage faculty members to explore novel teaching strategies, engage in industry collaborations, and contribute to research that has real-world applications. Entrepreneurial performance relies on creativity, risk-taking, and strategic decision-making, enabling educators to identify opportunities and implement effective solutions [15]. Professors who embrace an entrepreneurial mindset integrate hands-on learning experiences, mentor student-led initiatives, and foster interdisciplinary cooperation. Institutions that prioritize entrepreneurship promote knowledge sharing, learning-driven cultures, and participatory decision-making to enhance institutional performance [16]. Such an approach not only benefits faculty development but also prepares students for the demands of an increasingly competitive workforce.

The impact of entrepreneurial performance extends to institutional growth, operational efficiency, and adaptability to emerging challenges [17]. Entrepreneurial institutions are better positioned to secure research funding, establish industry partnerships, and enhance student employability. By integrating entrepreneurial principles, universities can refine internal processes, innovate curricula, and foster a culture of continuous improvement. External factors, including economic conditions, governmental policies, and social trends, significantly influence institutional entrepreneurial performance [18], [19]. Universities that align their strategic goals with market needs and policy frameworks can maximize opportunities for expansion and innovation. Supportive policies that encourage academic entrepreneurship, create innovation hubs, and strengthen university-industry linkages play a crucial role in fostering sustainable growth.

Entrepreneurial leadership is a driving force behind institutional success, requiring creativity, vision, and adaptability [20]. Effective leaders inspire faculty members to embrace change, experiment with emerging pedagogical models, and pursue cross-disciplinary research collaborations. While research on entrepreneurial leadership remains limited, existing studies highlight its significance in shaping forward-thinking academic institutions [21], [22]. Leaders who champion faculty development, encourage strategic partnerships, and implement evidence-based decision-making foster resilience and innovation within their institutions. By cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset among educators, universities can create a dynamic learning environment that prepares students to navigate the complexities of modern industries. Strong leadership ensures that institutions remain agile, competitive, and equipped to address future challenges, securing their long-term relevance in the global education landscape.

The purpose of this study is to assess the teaching competencies of faculty members at Hashemite University and examine the relationship between these competencies and their self-reported entrepreneurial performance. The study aims to identify current levels of teaching competencies across various domains—including personal, academic, administrative, cultural, and professional—and to understand how these competencies influence faculty members' ability to perform entrepreneurial activities within higher education. This research is important because it addresses a gap in understanding how teaching competencies impact entrepreneurial outcomes, an area increasingly relevant as universities worldwide strive to foster innovation and entrepreneurship. The novelty of this study lies in its focus on linking competency evaluation

within a quality assurance framework to entrepreneurial performance, offering a unique perspective that can inform faculty development initiatives and enhance educational quality at Hashemite University and beyond.

This study was carried out in response to the recommendations received from different conferences by emphasizing the necessity for faculty development programs because of lack of teaching competencies which leads their poor performance [3], [4], [23], [24]. Consistent with these findings, the present study seeks to evaluate the level of teaching competencies held by faculty members at Hashemite University and to examine the link between those competencies and their perceived entrepreneurial performance. Therefore, this research poses the following questions:

- To what extent do faculty members possess teaching competencies at the Hashemite University from their point of view?
- What is the level of entrepreneurial performance of faculty members at the Hashemite University from their point of view?
- Is there a relationship between the level of faculty members' possession of teaching competencies and the level of their entrepreneurial performance from their point of view?

2. METHOD

2.1. Population and sample

All the Hashemite University's faculty members comprise the study population, which totals 882 individuals. The study sample, which numbered 340 faculty members and represented (39%) of the community overall, was made up of 191 males and 149 females, with the majority of professors (80), associate professors (122), and assistant professors (138). To determine an adequate sample size for this study, we aimed to ensure representation of the entire population of 882 faculty members at Hashemite University. The selected sample size of 340 faculty members, representing 39% of the total population, meets established guidelines for ensuring reliability and generalizability in social science research. According to Krejcie and Morgan [25], for a population of approximately 900 individuals, a sample size of around 269 would be adequate to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error. By selecting a sample of 340 faculty members, we exceeded this minimum requirement, thus enhancing the statistical power and ensuring a higher level of precision in our findings.

2.2. Research instruments

To fulfill the aim of the study, a questionnaire was developed that consisted of two parts. The first, to identify the degree of faculty members' possession of teaching competencies at the Hashemite University, based on previous studies [3], [4], [26]; and the second to measure the level of leadership performance of faculty members at the Hashemite University, after referring to a number of studies [23], [24], [27]. The questionnaire adopted a five-point Likert scale (5=strongly agree; 4=agree; 3=neutral; 2=I do not agree; 1=never agree)

The final questionnaire was presented to a panel of experts in order to assess its content validity. The experts judged whether the items were appropriate, clear, and expressed in correct language and on a four-point scale. Their job was to propose changes as needed. According to this feedback, the questionnaire was revised and tuned accordingly and finalized based on that for using as an outcome instrument. We assessed the reliability of the instrument using Cronbach's alpha to determine how the items in each domain were inter-related. The results of the analysis revealed a Cronbach alpha=0.90 for items related to teaching competencies and 0.94 for items measuring entrepreneurial performance, this showed good internal consistency within the sub-scales.

2.3. Data collection and analysis

Data for this study were gathered by visiting faculty members at the Hashemite University. They were required to sign a consent form stating their willingness to take part in this study. Utilizing SPSS version 21, analysis was carried out. Arithmetic means and standard deviation were utilized for descriptive statistics, and the correlation coefficient was determined using Pearson's correlation coefficient for inferential statistics.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first research question examined the extent to which faculty members at Hashemite University exhibit teaching competencies. Analysis of the responses indicated that faculty perceived their overall teaching competencies to be at a "moderate" level, with an average mean of 3.49 and a standard deviation of 0.56. The ranking of competency domains was as: personal and academic competencies tied for the highest rank (mean=3.52), while administrative and cultural competencies ranked next (mean=3.47), and professional competencies received the lowest rank (mean=3.44), yet all were categorized as moderate Table 1.

Table 1. Level of teaching competency

Variables	Mean	SD	Degree
Personal competencies	3.52	0.57	Moderate
Academic competencies	3.52	0.46	Moderate
Administrative competencies	3.47	0.59	Moderate
Cultural competencies	3.47	0.67	Moderate
Professional competencies	3.44	0.58	Moderate
Total	3.49	0.56	Moderate

This finding suggests that faculty members recognize their teaching competencies as moderate, potentially in comparison to international standards set by top-ranked universities. Many respondents have completed their postgraduate education at European institutions, where they closely observed advanced teaching competencies, leading to a moderate self-assessment. Moreover, financial constraints in Jordanian universities, including Hashemite University, impact various aspects such as resource allocation, research funding, and faculty development initiatives. This is consistent with previous studies [9], [11], [22], [24]. However, our findings contradict those reported in other studies [1], [3], [4], [23], [25]–[27], which indicated high levels of teaching competencies among faculty members.

The second research question addressed the level of perceived entrepreneurial performance among faculty at Hashemite University. The results showed a moderate rating of entrepreneurial performance, with a grand mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 0.58. This is aligned with the moderate teaching competencies identified, suggesting that the level of teaching competencies directly influences entrepreneurial performance. Improved teaching competencies may lead to enhanced entrepreneurial outcomes, aligning with Hashemite University's commitment to total quality in education. Conversely, several studies [28]–[33] reported medium entrepreneurial performance among faculty members, while other studies [20], [23], [27]–[38] indicated high performance levels in their respective institutions.

Table 2 displays the results of the Pearson correlation coefficient between teaching competencies and the level of entrepreneurial performance among faculty members in the colleges of the Hashemite University. The following are the results of the Pearson correlation coefficient based on the responses of the study sample that measure the relation between teaching competencies and the level of entrepreneurial performance for faculty members at Hashemite University. The overall correlation coefficient had a value of 0.89, indicating that there is a strong positive relationship between the two variables.

The third research question explored the relationship between teaching competencies and entrepreneurial performance. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to assess the strength and direction of this association, as summarized in Table 2. The overall correlation coefficient of 0.89 suggests a strong positive relationship between teaching competencies and entrepreneurial performance. This implies that as faculty members' teaching competencies increase, so too does their entrepreneurial performance. This may mean that the higher the level of teaching competencies among the faculty members, the higher the level of their entrepreneurial performance, and vice versa. Hence, Hashemite University is trying to adopt the principles of total quality through selecting and retaining highly competent faculty members in teaching, which helps in turn to enhance their entrepreneurial performance and increase the competitive advantage of the university at both the local and international levels.

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficient between teaching competencies and the level of entrepreneurial performance

Variables	Entrepreneurial performance
Personal competencies	0.79*
Academic competencies	0.82*
Administrative competencies	0.84*
Cultural competencies	0.85*
Professional competencies	0.85*
Teaching competencies	0.089*

*p=0.01

According to Roick and Ringeisen [3] and supported by Reichert *et al.* [2], the competencies that faculty members need to acquire and possess are closely linked to their entrepreneurial performance, and Hashemite University's adoption of total quality principles aims to select and retain highly competent faculty, enhancing their entrepreneurial capabilities and ultimately boosting the university's competitive advantage at both local and international levels. This is supported by previous researchers [2], [3], who emphasize the close link between necessary competencies and entrepreneurial performance. Furthermore,

Reichert *et al.* [2] underscores the importance of faculty possessing adequate skills to perform effectively within academic settings. The majority of studies in this area indicate a positive correlation between teaching competencies and entrepreneurial performance, reinforcing the significance of our findings. The moderate levels of teaching competencies suggest that while faculty members are proficient, there remains potential for growth to reach higher standards. This finding may imply that faculty training initiatives are needed to bridge gaps between current competencies and those observed in top-ranking institutions

4. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the critical role of teaching competencies-including personal, academic, administrative, cultural, and professional domains-in fostering entrepreneurial performance among faculty members at Hashemite University. The findings demonstrate that while current competency levels are moderate, there is a positive and significant relationship between these competencies and entrepreneurial outcomes. This suggests that universities, particularly those aiming to encourage innovation, should consider evaluating and developing teaching competencies as a key component of faculty performance reviews. By integrating these competencies within quality assurance frameworks, institutions can better support the dual goals of academic excellence and entrepreneurial readiness. Several recommendations emerge from these findings. First, teaching competencies should be included as a core criterion in the evaluation of faculty performance, with a balanced emphasis on both material and moral incentives to motivate and recognize faculty achievements. Additionally, identifying faculty members' specific training needs and organizing targeted professional development initiatives can greatly enhance their teaching and entrepreneurial skills.

In conclusion, the novelty of this study lies in its pioneering effort to examine the relationship between faculty teaching competencies and entrepreneurial performance through a quality assurance lens. This approach provides valuable insights into the development of effective faculty training programs aimed at enhancing both teaching quality and entrepreneurial activities in universities. The findings from this study could inform policy and practice at Hashemite University and other higher education institutions, leading to more effective strategies for fostering entrepreneurial mindsets among faculty members. Future research could focus on assessing the effectiveness of specific training interventions in enhancing teaching competencies and entrepreneurial outcomes. Additionally, exploring how competency-based evaluations influence institutional performance could provide valuable insights for shaping policies that prioritize both educational quality and innovation.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Authors state no funding involved.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Hytham M. Bany Issa	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓				
Zohair H. Al-Zoubi	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓				
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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : **O**riginal Draft

E : **E**diting

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [OTB], upon reasonable request.

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